

Royal Hittite Religion

By Tayfun Bilgin, NA

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Just as its contemporaries in the Late Bronze Age, Hittite state had a polytheist religion. The pantheon included hundreds of deities, which grew over time with the deities various cultures (e.g. Hattians, Palaeans, Luwians, Hurrians, etc.) that were incorporated through conquest or close contact, so much so that Hittites referred to their pantheon in general as the “Thousand Gods of Hatti,” the last word being a reference to their country. While the actual number of gods and goddesses may not reach a thousand, if all divine beings, like the demons (mythological creatures, animals, mixed beings) and topographical features (mountains, rivers, springs, etc.) included, the number certainly exceeds a thousand. The top deities of the pantheon were the Sun-deities, both male and female, and the Storm-gods. Syncretism only occurred in a limited fashion in the later periods of the empire. Thus, many local gods were distinguished from similar deities, resulting in numerous variations by location, e.g. Storm God of Hatti, Storm God of Zippalanda, Storm God of Nerik, etc. The divine world was conceived as a mirror of the human world, where anthropomorphic deities were organized in a hierarchy of various families and like humans had needs to eat, sleep, and even be entertained. Temples were the houses of the deities where they inhabited an image, typically an anthropomorphic statue, but in some occasions it could also be a zoomorphic statue, a worked or unworked stele, or even a manufactured symbol, such as a golden disk for a Sun deity. Of course, such man-made objects would only be inhabited by the deities through special rituals. While the most prominent gods, the Sun-deities and the Storm-gods were responsible for the essence of life with their sun-light and waters, other deities presided over various matters like warfare, birth, death, reproduction, love, and so forth. Since almost all of the written documentation of Hittites originates from the administrative archives of the Hittite state, what we know of their beliefs pertains almost entirely to the official cult of the state that was headed by the king and the royal family. The king as the high priest of all the deities had a special role between the gods and the humans. He had to ensure the deities of the land were served and taken care of by the people of Hatti, so that the deities would take care of the land and the people. To that effect the state maintained numerous temples all over the land for various deities. While not many Hittite cities have been explored, at their capital city Hattusa, modern day Boğazkale in central Turkey, ruins of over 30 temples have been unearthed. The administration ensured that temples all over Hatti were adequately staffed and maintained and the deities were properly served, which included daily ritual offerings. The temples were an extension of the state administration. They were provided by property and personnel, including slaves, to maintain their own economies, but were definitely not independent of the state. Annually, seasonally, or monthly, over a hundred religious festivals were conducted by the state cult throughout the year. The king was responsible in guiding all societal religious activities. He and/or royal family members regularly travelled to various locations to attend the festival ceremonies. In festivals, deities are praised, provided with offerings, entertained with singers, dancers, and even sports activities, and in some instances the images of the deities were paraded in processions giving the public a rare opportunity to view them, who normally remained in the inner sancta of the temples accessible only to a select few. To oversee his duties properly, the king had to communicate with the gods, which was accomplished through various divinatory methods, such as extispicy, augury, lot oracles, dream incubation, or by interpreting unsolicited omens. Cultic specialists were experienced with numerous rituals that were performed for rite de passage like birth, puberty, marriage, death, or to treat illnesses and ailments. The funerals of the royal family involved cremation of the body. The dead kings and other royal family members were believed have “become gods,” and passed into the divine domain for a pleasant afterlife.

Date Range: 1650 BCE - 1180 BCE

Region: Central Anatolia

Region tags: Asia Minor, Turkey, Anatolia

Approximate borders of the core area of the Hittite Kingdom in the 13th century BCE, excluding the vassal kingdoms.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Taracha, Piotr. Religions of Second Millennium Anatolia (Dresdner Beiträge zur Hethitologie 27), Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2009
- Source 2: Haas, Volkert. Geschichte Der Hethitischen Religion. Leiden: Brill, 1994.
- Source 3: de Martino, Stefano (ed.) Handbook Hittite Empire, Berlin: De Gruyter, 2020.

Notes: A summary treatment of Hittite religion: Beckman, Gary. "Hittite Religion." In The Cambridge History of Religion in the Ancient World, edited by Michele Renée Salzman and Marvin A. Sweeney, 84-101. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. General treatments of Hittite culture: Bryce, Trevor. Life and Society in the Hittite World. Oxford: Oxford University, 2002. Collins, Billie Jean. The Hittites and Their World. Atlanta: SBL Press, 2007.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/HPM/index.php>
- Source 1 Description: Hethitologie Portal Mainz (numerous resources about hittitology)
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.encyclopedia.com/environment/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/hittite-religion>
- Source 2 Description: A description of various aspects of Hittite religion, gods, myths.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.hethport.uni-wuerzburg.de/HPM/index.php>
- Source 1 Description: Hethitologie Portal Mainz (look for links to primary sources under 'Text Corpora')
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.adwmainz.de/projekte/corpus-der-hethitischen-festrituale/informationen.html>
- Source 2 Description: Das Corpus der hethitischen Festrutuale
- Source 3 URL: <https://hittitetexts.com/en>
- Source 3 Description: The Leiden Electronic Corpus of Hittite Texts

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: But not on religious matters

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: But not over religious matters

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The king and thus the state themselves are the power behind the state cult.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Either paid or provided the means to support themselves.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: The Hittite king is also the high priest of the state cult.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: The temples and cultic institutions have their own permanent priests and personnel. King and occasionally other royal family members officiate the religious ceremonies. Many political officials attend the religious ceremonies too, but they are not considered as religious officials.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: State enforces on its cultic personnel that the deities of the state cult are served and observed properly. There is no enforcement of observance on the common public as they are not involved in the state cult.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: Temples were provided with various types of property and donations. The king was able to issue exemptions from tax and/or obligations to various individuals and institutions including cultic ones, but the fact that there are such decrees indicates that the exemptions were not applicable to cultic institutions by default. For various examples of exemptions in Hittite texts, see Imparati (1974: 148–170).

Reference: Imparati, Fiorella. “Una Concessione Di Terre Da Parte Di Tudhaliya IV” 32, no. 1 (1974). <https://doi.org/10.3406/rhita.1974.1075>. p.148–170

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: While it may not be defined as apostasy, neglect or ignorance of cultic duties by the cultic personnel occurs, and these are prosecuted by the state officials and believed to be punished divinely by the deities.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population,

numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If we leave aside the common public, I would assume that the adherents of the state cult would include the royal family, the state officials and personnel of the cultic institutions. There must have been hundreds of temples that the state maintained in numerous cities. So a very rough estimate would be in several thousands.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– I don't know

Notes: It is difficult to place the Hittite state cult in such a classification. While the state cult is a large establishment spread over the land, the number of people in its organization is small in comparison to the overall population. And we know little about the religion of the commoners. There are thousands of deities and people likely have their own personal deities that they worship.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: But not in the sense of a network. Within a particular temple there is a hierarchy among its priests and personnel, but other than the king and royal family as the overall leaders of the cult, the temples are largely independent of each other.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The single leader would be the king as the high priest of the state. We encounter titles like "Great Priest" used for some officials, but the nature and capacity of these officials are unclear. There are occasions where the king did appoint some princes as the "Great Priest" of the cult of a god of certain locations (e.g., Kizzuwatna and Aleppo) in which case the assigned prince has a de facto governorship role beside his leadership in the local cult.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– I don't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

Notes: King chooses his successor, thus the next high priest.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

Notes: It is known from some instruction texts that the king/palace has the power to assign the priests or authorize the local administrators to assign priests to the temples. It is also possible that in some cases priesthood as a profession may have passed from father to son in some families.

Reference: Taggar-Cohen, Ada. Hittite Priesthood. Texte Der Hethiter 26. Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2006.

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– I don't know

Notes: I don't know. This is unlikely to be the standard method of assigning a religious official, but it is plausible that in some occasion installation of a certain person could have been verified by divination. There are some oracle texts that checks whether the installation of a certain person (to an unknown office) is approved by the gods.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Even the king himself admits mistakes or questions his conduct such as in terms of proper observation or breach of oaths.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: The king's word is absolute, but as mentioned above the king himself can question his own conduct or admit mistakes.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: Not in the sense of sacred writings. There are numerous rituals, prayers, myths, etc

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: This is very difficult to estimate, as very few Hittite settlements have been explored and even those have not been completely excavated.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 4663

Notes: Building C in Kusakli, the Hittite city of Sarissa, is 4,663 m². The Great Temple at the Hittite capital covers an area of 2,400 m², but with its storage facilities and administrative buildings, the temple complex covers 26,000 m².

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The Great Temple is estimated to be about 5 meters in height. Most Hittite buildings were not higher than 2 or 3 stories.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: I will roughly guess the average size of the thirty temples in the capital city around 600-700 square meters.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Notes: One or two stories.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: In the Hittite capital, within the walled city, so far 31 temples have been uncovered. Even then, it is difficult to judge what area around the temples was within their temenos. Also, apparently not all temples were active at the same period. That said, with a very rough estimate, I would suggest the temples and their surrounding areas cover at least 10 percent of the walled city (About 27 ha of 270 ha). One should note that the actual settlement did extend beyond the walls.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Reference: van den Hout, Theo P. J. . "Tombs and Memorials: The (divine) Stone-house and Hegur Reconsidered". In *Recent Developments in Hittite Archaeology and History. Papers in Memory of Hans G. Güterbock*, 73–91. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns, 2002.

Reference: Groddek, Detlev. "‘mausoleum’ (É.NA4) Und ‘totentempel’ (éhištā) Im Hethitischen". *Ugarit Forschungen* 33 (2001): 213-18.

Reference: Cammarosano, Michele. "Huwaši. Cult Stelae and Stela Shrines in Hittite Anatolia". In *Natur Und Kult in Anatolien*, 303-32. *BYZAS* 24. Istanbul: Ege, 2019.

Reference: Steitler, Charles. "Sacred Springs, Spring Sanctuaries and Spring-deities in Hittite Religion". In *Natur Und Kult in Anatolien*, 1-25. *BYZAS* 24. Istanbul: Ege, 2019.

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Structures referred to as "Stone-house" in Hittite texts were apparently where the cremated remains of royal family members were kept. No such structure has been identified definitely in the archaeological record. Chamber B of Yazılıkaya sanctuary might be a mausoleum for the Hittite king Tudhaliya IV.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: Few Hittite cemeteries have been identified and none are royal or monumental.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Various locations both urban and rural could be associated with certain rituals and festivals. Several festivals include a banquet attended by a large number of dignitaries and officials that take place in the structure called "halentuwa" which existed in various cities, probably as part of the palace or temple building. (Taracha, 2017: 101-110). Also, various natural structures, such as rock outcrops, mountain tops, springs, caves were considered to have a sacred aura and were locations of rituals.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Rock sanctuaries called hekur, probably rocky outcrops, mountain tops; Cult steles called huwasi-stones that could be in various locations, typically in open-air shrines.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– Some public spaces

– I don't know

Notes: Many personal seals do include religious iconography. Also, some monuments with religious iconography are in public space.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

Notes: Not explicit. A king shown in the embrace of a god might be interpreted that way.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– I don't know

Notes: There may not be doctrine to talk about, but in terms of symbolism, certain deities were associated with certain animals, such as Storm-God with a bull, Tutelary deity with a Stag, etc. Depictions of the deities with such animals can be seen in reliefs,

seals. In monumental architecture, the only writing used was with Anatolian hieroglyphs, in which a DEUS sign (an oval shape divided vertically in the middle) precedes the divine names. Also in Anatolian hieroglyphs certain symbols are used to refer to certain deities, such as a W shaped sign for the Storm God, a Stag or just an antler for the Protective God Inara, etc. A determinative of divinity is also present in cuneiform writing.

↳ Humans:
– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: In Hittite belief all mountains, rivers, springs were divine entities. Even certain rock formations, sink holes, caves etc did have sacred aura.

Reference: Collins, Billie Jean. *The Hittites and Their World*. Atlanta: SBL Press, 2007. p.162

Reference: D'Agostino, Anacleto, Valentina Orsi, and Giulia Torri, eds.. *Sacred Landscapes of Hittites and Luwians: Proceedings of the International Conference in Honour of Franca Pecchioli Daddi*, Florence, February 6th-8th 2014. Edited by Anacleto D'Agostino, Valentina Orsi, and Giulia Torri. *Studia Asiana* 9. Firenze: Firenze University, 2015.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: There were numerous periodical cultic festivals celebrated throughout the year that took place in temples of various cities. The king or another member of the royal family had to attend to some of these festivals. For some festivals taking place at the capital Hattusa, state officials from other cities had to travel to Hattusa.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Reference: Collins, Billie Jean. *The Hittites and Their World*. Atlanta: SBL Press, 2007. p.192-194

Reference: Archi, Alfonso. "The Soul Has to Leave the Land of the Living". *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religions* 7 (2007): 169-95. p.183

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The fact that the body was often cremated indicates that the spirit was independent of it. Yet, after the cremation the bones were gathered and placed on a seat and offerings of food and drinks are made in front of it.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Even the deities and animals were deemed to have both a body and a spirit.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no canonical set of beliefs. On the one hand, similar to Mesopotamia, in Hittite culture there is an afterworld "below," in the "dark earth" that is gloomy and unpleasant. While, unlike the ordinary man, the Hittite king or queen became gods upon death, there are references about heading to a 'dark earth' even concerning the kings. Yet, in the ritual for the dead king there is a reference about going to a meadow filled with animals in the afterlife. This notion is supported with funeral gifts of a symbolic piece of turf, farming equipment and sacrificed animals.

Reference: Haas, Volkert. *Geschichte Der Hethitischen Religion*. Leiden: Brill, 1994. p.216-229

Reference: Bryce, Trevor. *Life and Society in the Hittite World*. Oxford: Oxford University, 2002. p.180-184

Reference: Kassian, Alexei, Andrej Korolëv, and Andrej Sidel'tsev. *Hittite Funerary Rituals, Šalliš Waštaiš*. *Alter Orient Und Altes Testament* 288. Münster: Ugarit-Verlag, 2002.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Not a lot is known about Hittite mortuary practices as few Hittite cemeteries have been explored. Nevertheless, supported by textual evidence, it appears the cremation was the preferred funeral method for the royal family. The few cemeteries inspected do not appear to be that of the elite or the royalty and have a mixture of cremation and internment burials.

Reference: Haas, Volkert. *Geschichte Der Hethitischen Religion*. Leiden: Brill, 1994. p.233–237

Reference: Seeher, Jürgen. "The Plateau: The Hittites". In *The Oxford Handbook of Ancient Anatolia*, edited by Gregory McMahon and Sharon Steadman. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780195376142.013.0016>. p.388–389

Reference: Bryce, Trevor. *Life and Society in the Hittite World*. Oxford: Oxford University, 2002. p.178–179

Reference: Axelsson, Anton. "Hittite Mortuary Practices". Thesis. Uppsala universitet, Institutionen för arkeologi och antik historia, 2017.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: Observed in very few instances

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: This does not appear to be a regular practice, but as understood from textual evidence there had been a few instances of carrying of the remains of dead kings to different locations.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals for royal funerals include sacrifices of cattle, sheep, horses and asses. Likewise, the few Hittite cemeteries (non-royal) that were investigated did reveal animal sacrifices cattle, sheep, pigs, dogs, occasionally horses.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Royal funeral rituals refer to symbolic items like a piece of turf and farming equipment

(generally interpreted as a symbolization of life in an afterlife meadow, as mentioned in the same ritual). Non-royal cemeteries have modest gifts like pottery, occasionally seals, few metal artifacts.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Almost nothing is known from the archaeological record, but textual record indicates valuable gifts (gold, silver, garments, etc) to the dead kings. Very few jewelry items were discovered in other cemeteries.

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Only known from textual record.

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Most common gift is pottery, occasionally seals, metal rings; spindle whorls in female graves.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: Remains of the Hittite kings were kept in buildings referred to as '(Divine) Stone House' (or in some cases a hekur-house). Nothing has been identified definitely in the archaeological record.

Reference: van den Hout, Theo P. J. . "Tombs and Memorials: The (divine) Stone-house and Hegur Reconsidered". In *Recent Developments in Hittite Archaeology and History. Papers in Memory of Hans G. Güterbock, 73-91*. Winona Lake, IN: Eisenbrauns, 2002.

↳ In cemetery:

– No

Notes: Few Hittite cemeteries have been identified and none are royal or monumental.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Remains of ancestral royal family members were kept together in the stone-house (hekur-house is also an interrelated but not identical funerary institution).

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: This existed and few examples are known from the Hittite capital Hattusa, but they are indicative of lower status.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: For non-royals, a mixture of cremations, pithos burials, pit graves, cist-graves are encountered.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Within the Hittite pantheon certain deities appear in supreme positions, but there is not a constant hierarchy. It can change according to time, place, and situation. Storm Gods and Sun deities tend to be in the leading roles.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Hittite deities are often depicted in human form, but occasionally they could be represented by non-human objects too, such as the Storm God with a bull or a Sun deity with a sun disk.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Storm Gods and the Sun deities are sky deities.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The king was in a liaison position between the gods and the people

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

Notes: Deities, including the supreme ones, could be good or bad.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Certain deities are associated with certain aspects of life, but does that mean they have no power over other matters? The Storm God is one of the top deities and as a weather deity he is associated with all weather events, but his knowledge and powers are not restricted to that alone.

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Notes: A concept of fate exists and there are even 'fate-deities' who record ones fate at birth, but whether that implies an entirely predetermined destiny and the supreme deities have knowledge of it is unclear.

Reference: Schwemer, Daniel. "Schicksal. B. Bei Den Hethitern.". *Reallexikon Der Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie* 12 (2009): 155-57.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: But it is not specific to the gods alone; humans also have causal efficacy.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Whether deities are pleased or angry could be questioned through divination.

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Whether deities are pleased or angry could be questioned through divination.

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Deities were served and ritually consumed food and drinks.

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Deities, including the supreme ones, were conceived in human terms. They required sustenance, they slept, dressed, met other gods, enjoyed entertainment; they had emotion; they could make mistakes, they could even be deceived.
 - Reference: Collins, Billie Jean. *The Hittites and Their World*. Atlanta: SBL Press, 2007. p.173-174

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Through omens.
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Both solicited (dream incubation) and unsolicited
 - ↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Certain people with such ability are referred to as 'one-of-god'.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: In numerous ways (extispicy, augury, lot oracles, etc.)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Some methods of communication require religious specialists, but dreams, omens can apply to anybody. Nevertheless religious specialists are almost always consulted for interpretation.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: Probably not. But there are effigies, statues that represent the dead.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: See above

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Notes: Presumably yes. There are oracle inquiries and rituals to pacify spirits of the dead who were angry due to unfulfilled vows.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– I don't know

Notes: Most references tend to deal with the anger of the dead spirits.

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

Notes: Satisfaction of the dead spirits through ritual treatments could be interpreted as a positive emotion.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: There are oracle texts and rituals that aim to investigate and undo the curses of certain dead members of the royal family.

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– I don't know

↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - Notes: As mentioned above, many topographical features like mountains, springs or even parts of temples (e.g. hearth, pillars) can be divine beings. Others, animals or mythological beings, are depicted in art.
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: In art/depictions

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - I don't know
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - I don't know
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - Yes
 - Notes: but only partially. There are hundreds of divine beings, originally from various cultures. They are not in a single large family of gods.
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
 - Notes: There is a loose sense of hierarchy, but it can change depending on time period, location, or situation. There is often an 'assembly of gods'.
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
 - Notes: More or less
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - Yes [specify]: Rather than a family, an assembly of gods is a more appropriate term for the Hittite pantheon.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: For examples of what the deities are angry or care about, see Beal (2002).

Reference: Beal, Richard. "Gleanings from Hittite Oracle Questions on Religion, Society, Psychology and Decision Making". In *Silva Anatolica: Anatolian Studies Presented to Maciej Popko on the Occasion of His 65th Birthday*, 11-37. Warsaw: Agade, 2002.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: They care about murder (i.e. consider it to be a sin) in general, not specifically of the coreligionists.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: See above

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: See above

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: Bestiality
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: if it is slander, gossip with malicious intent.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: particularly when persons are in contact with the gods (e.g. in temples)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: hygiene and purity of the temple environment;

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The agent and reason of punishments were typically determined by divination.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– I don't know

↳ Done randomly:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: Probably not. Our knowledge about how the afterlife was conceived is limited. But what can be derived from available evidence is that, similar to Mesopotamia, in Hittite culture there is an afterworld “below,” in the “dark earth” that is gloomy and unpleasant, where the dead eat mud and drink dirty water. However, that may not be taken as a “punishment” since it applies to all of the dead, regardless of their good deeds or sins. Also, the sins of the dead do carry over into the surviving family, and unless the family members make amends, they suffer the punishment in their lifetime. Thus, it seems punishment in the afterlife is not an emphasized concept if it exists at all.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Gods' punishment was sought as a reason behind everything negative in life. I suppose what is considered 'highly' is debatable, but the fact that the state organized a wide network of temples and cultic institutions, and spent considerable amount of money and manpower to maintain it, should testify to the importance that had been laid on satisfying the deities and consequently avoid punishment. It is notable that of the Hittite textual corpus of thousands of tablets, over 85% are on cultic matters.

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - Notes: If “sensory displeasure” implies injury, disability, ailment, such as problems with sight, speech, etc.

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - Notes: If “sensory displeasure” implies injury, disability, ailment, such as problems with sight, speech, etc.

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The sins carry forward in the family. It was believed that the son could be punished due to the misgivings of the father.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– I don't know

↳ Done randomly:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Long life (although that could go under 'enhanced health' too)

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: and No. Social norms are expected to be obeyed and deities can be a part of the enforcement process, but there is not a prescription.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Many of the virtues listed here pretty much apply to the society in general and are not religion specific. That said the most important virtues highlighted in temple instructions are personal cleanliness, ritual purity, and integrity.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: There is plenty of evidence that even the priests did have their own families.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Votive gifts of valuable items and other property are common, but this is not a requirement.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: While King and/or his family had to spend a considerable time attending periodical festivals, the cultic personnel were responsible for the daily rituals as well.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: Ethical precepts apply to the society in general, they are not particularly a religious requirement.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: It cannot be called private or household, but in all temples of the state cult there are small scale rituals of feeding of the deities at least once a day.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Notes: Probaby in tens to hundreds

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: For large scale rituals I take festivals as a reference, and there are over a hundred festivals in a calendar year. Some are celebrated annually, some seasonally, some monthly, and they can be in various locations and can last multiple days.

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The fact that step-by-step manuals of many festivals and rituals were kept in writing indicates that correct conduct was important. There are even oracle texts that indicate deities were queried about their approval/disapproval about certain deviations from the regular festival details.

Reference: Beal, Richard. "Gleanings from Hittite Oracle Questions on Religion, Society, Psychology and Decision Making". In *Silva Anatolica: Anatolian Studies Presented to Maciej Popko on the Occasion of His 65th Birthday*, 11-37. Warsaw: Agade, 2002. p.22-23

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Many festivals are celebrated with the participation of the royalty and numerous officials.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Many rituals involve drinking beer or wine, but not in excessive amounts.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The Hittite polity should be defined as an empire, and the state cult did include numerous deities of various cultures (Hittite, Hattian, Luwian, Hurrian, etc.)

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through the state. Note that there is not clear boundary between the state and the state cult.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state does provide the means for temples to take care of the personnel and the property.

Reference: Taggar-Cohen, Ada. Hittite Priesthood. Texte Der Hethiter 26. Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2006. p.436

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not much is known regarding the training of the cult officials. In some instances it is known that priesthood continued within the family and it could include both sons and daughters, and in such cases it is possible that the training was given within the family. Yet, there is no indication that the priesthood was restricted to certain families.

Reference: Taggar-Cohen, Ada. Hittite Priesthood. Texte Der Hethiter 26. Heidelberg: Universitätsverlag Winter, 2006. p.436

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than

the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See above

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: State and the state cult go hand in hand and act in a formal bureaucracy. Within the temples there are various levels of priests and functionaries that interact in a bureaucracy of their own.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: State and the state cult go hand in hand and act in a formal bureaucracy.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: Temples did have their own storage facilities, but these were for self consumption. See also next answer.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological evidence indicates that the state had large food storage facilities.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state did provide the infrastructure for the water management.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other

than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state provided the infrastructure for roads, bridges, etc.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: However, again, there is not a clear boundary between the state and the state cult. The taxes and tithes are levied by the state, but in some places the institutions of the state cult may have been instrumental in the collection of the taxes and tithes on behalf of the state.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See above.

Reference: Klinger, Jörg. "Hittite Economics". In *Handbook Hittite Empire*, 605–45. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2020. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110661781-013>.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state and the state cult are intertwined. The state officials act as the police force.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They were subject to the state laws. There are written copies of a collection of Hittite laws, but these cannot be referred to as a formal code. Much like the Code of Hammurabi, the written Hittite Code is not comprehensive and is more like a collection of common law clauses. Also it is a secular and straightforward document with no indications of religious or royal propaganda. In practice, the state laws were most likely customary laws in general.

Reference: Bryce, Trevor. *Life and Society in the Hittite World*. Oxford: Oxford University, 2002. p.32-55

Reference: Collins, Billie Jean. *The Hittites and Their World*. Atlanta: SBL Press, 2007. p.118-123

Reference: Hoffner Jr, Harry A. *The Laws of the Hittites*. Leiden: Brill, 1997.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The unclear separation of the state and state cult complicates the answer. The temples did not have a military component. But they were part of the state cult, and of course the state did have institutionalized military.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The royalty and the officials of the administration naturally had institutionalized military obligations. The temple personnel probably did not have such duties.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: by the military of the state, see the comment in the previous question.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: However, literacy was not common in the Hittite society. It is a job scribes specialize in. We don't know how literate the kings, queens, and other nobility were. They may have had basic abilities.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: See above.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: The Hittites used a calendar but it is not specific to the religious group.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The calendar was the same as what the state administration used.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Temples of the state cult were provided with land, orchards, and slaves. Land could be leased to farmers who provided a share of the crop to the temples.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The adherents of the group are the royal family, the upper echelons of the administration and the cultic personnel. There is not a clear boundary between the cult and the state. It is possible that, when needed, the state provided food to the temples as well as that the temples provided any surplus from their assigned lands to the state.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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